

Supplementary data for **Figure 4**: List of reference studies

1. Y.H. Lin, M.Z. Lin, Y.Q. Chen, H.Q. Tian, Isolation of male and female gametes, zygotes and proembryos of leek (*Allium tuberosum* Roxb). *Zygote* **28**, 278 (2020).
2. T. Hirano, Y. Hoshino, Detection of changes in the nuclear phase and evaluation of male germ units by flow cytometry during in vitro pollen tube growth in *Alstroemeria aurea*. *Journal of Plant Research* **122**, 225 (2009).
3. T. Hirano, Y. Hoshino, Sperm dimorphism in terms of nuclear shape and microtubule accumulation in *Cyrtanthus mackenii*. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **23**, 153 (2010).
4. K.R. Shivanna, H. Xu, P. Taylor, R.B. Knox, Isolation of sperms from the pollen tubes of flowering plants during fertilization. *Plant Physiology* **87**, 647 (1988).
5. M. Yong-sheng, Y. Hong-yuan, Isolation and fusion of sperm cells in several bicellular pollen species. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **34**, 688 (1992).
6. D.D. Cass, An ultrastructural and Nomarski-interference study of the sperms of barley. *Canadian Journal of Botany* **51**, 601 (1973).
7. Z. Chen, G. Zhu, Z. Cao, Isolation and purification of viable sperm cells from stored bicellular pollen of *Lilium davidii* Duch. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **5**, 32 (1995).
8. X. Zhao, N. Yang, T. Wang, Comparative proteomic analysis of generative and sperm cells reveals molecular characteristics associated with sperm development and function specialization. *Journal of Proteome Research* **12**, 5058 (2013).
9. D. Southworth, S. Kwiatkowski, Arabinogalactan proteins at the cell surface of Brassica sperm and Lilium sperm and generative cells. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **9**, 269 (1996).
10. H.M. Van der Maas *et al.*, Cytological characterization of isolated sperm cells of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.). *Protoplasma* **178**, 48 (1994).
11. H.M. van der Maas, M.A.C.M. Zaal, E.R. de Jong, J.L. van Went, F.A. Krens, Optimization of isolation and storage of sperm cells from pollen of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.). *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **6**, 64 (1993).
12. Y.N. Zhang *et al.*, Isolation of male and female gametes of rice. *Crop Science* **50**, 2457 (2010).
13. S.N. Anderson *et al.*, Transcriptomes of isolated *Oryza sativa* gametes characterized by deep sequencing: evidence for distinct sex-dependent chromatin and epigenetic states before fertilization. *The Plant Journal* **76**, 729 (2013).
14. S.D. Russell *et al.*, Genomic profiling of rice sperm cell transcripts reveals conserved and distinct elements in the flowering plant male germ lineage. *New Phytologist* **195**, 560 (2012).
15. M. Khalequzzaman, N. Haq, Isolation and in vitro fusion of egg and sperm cells in *Oryza sativa*. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* **43**, 69 (2005).
16. M. Abiko *et al.*, Identification of proteins enriched in rice egg or sperm cells by single-cell proteomics. *PLoS one* **8**, e69578 (2013).
17. T. Uchiumi, I. Uemura, T. Okamoto, Establishment of an in vitro fertilization system in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Planta* **226**, 581 (2007).
18. X. Gou, S. Wang, F. Chen, Isolation and cytological observation of viable sperm cells of rice. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **41**, 669 (1999).
19. C. Li *et al.*, Genome-wide redistribution of 24-nt siRNAs in rice gametes. *Genome Research* **30**, 173 (2020).
20. Y. Ohnishi, I. Kokubu, T. Kinoshita, T. Okamoto, Sperm entry into the egg cell induces the progression of karyogamy in rice zygotes. *Plant and Cell Physiology* **60**, 1656 (2019).
21. E. Toda, Y. Ohnishi, T. Okamoto, Development of polyspermic rice zygotes. *Plant Physiology* **171**, 206 (2016).
22. Y. Ohnishi, T. Okamoto, Microscopic Observation, Three-dimensional reconstruction, and volume measurements of sperm nuclei. *Bio-protocol* **5**, e1437 (2015).
23. S. Zhou *et al.*, DNA demethylases remodel DNA methylation in rice gametes and zygote and are required for reproduction. *Molecular Plant* **14**, 1569 (2021).

24. X.P. Gou, L. Tang, F. Yan, F. Chen, Representative cDNA library from isolated rice sperm cells. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **43**, 1093 (2001).
25. W. Deng, C. Cheng, C. Luo, S.J. Yang, Isolation of the sperm and egg cells in wild rice (*Oryza officinalis*) as a mechanism for crop improvement. *Plant Reproduction* **33**, 35 (2020).
26. H. Yang, C. Zhou, Isolation of viable sperms from pollen of *Brassica napus*, *Zea mays* and *Secale cereale*. *Chinese Journal of Botany* **1**, 80 (1989).
27. E. Toda, T. Kiba, N. Kato, T. Okamoto, Isolation of gametes and zygotes from *Setaria viridis*. *Journal of Plant Research* **135**, 627 (2022).
28. D.X. Li, H.Y. Hu, Z.G. Ru, H.Q. Tian, Wheat egg in vitro fusion with wheat and green bristlegrass sperm. *Zygote* **27**, 126 (2019).
29. T. Maryenti, N. Kato, M. Ichikawa, T. Okamoto, Establishment of an in vitro fertilization system in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Plant & Cell Physiology* **60**, 835 (2019).
30. E. Szakacs, B. Barnabas, Sperm cell isolation from wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). Characterization of male transmission units in higher plants. *MTA, Budapest*, 37 (1990).
31. E. Matthys-Rochon, P. Vergne, S. Detchepare, C. Dumas, Male germ unit isolation from three tricellular pollen species: *Brassica oleracea*, *Zea mays*, and *Triticum aestivum*. *Plant Physiology* **83**, 464 (1987).
32. M. Kovács, B. Barnabás, E. Kranz, Electro-fused isolated wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) gametes develop into multicellular structures. *Plant Cell Reports* **15**, 178 (1995).
33. D. Southworth *et al.*, Antibodies to flowering-plant sperm. *Protoplasma* **208**, 115 (1999).
34. D.D. Cass, G.C. Fabi, Structure and properties of sperm cells isolated from the pollen of *Zea mays*. *Canadian Journal of Botany* **66**, 819 (1988).
35. I. Dupuis, P. Roedel, E. Matthys-Rochon, C. Dumas, Procedure to isolate viable sperm cells from corn (*Zea mays* L.) pollen grains. *Plant Physiology* **85**, 876 (1987).
36. V.T. Wagner, C. Dumas, H.L. Mogensen, Morphometric analysis of isolated *Zea mays* sperm. *Journal of Cell Science* **93**, 179 (1989).
37. P. Roedel, C. Dumas, Survival at 20° C and cryopreservation of isolated sperm cells from *Zea mays* pollen grains. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **6**, 212 (1993).
38. G. Zhang, M.K. Campenot, L.E. McGann, D.D. Cass, Flow cytometric characteristics of sperm cells isolated from pollen of *Zea mays*. *Plant Physiology* **99**, 54 (1992).
39. G. Zhang, D.J. Gifford, D.D. Cass, RNA and protein synthesis in sperm cells isolated from *Zea mays* L. pollen. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **6**, 239 (1993).
40. G. Zhang, C.M. Williams, M.K. Campenot, L.E. McGann, D.D. Cass, Improvement of longevity and viability of sperm cells isolated from pollen of *Zea mays*. *Plant Physiology* **100**, 47 (1992).
41. E. Matthys-Rochon, R. Møl, P. Heizmann, C. Dumas, Isolation and microinjection of active sperm nuclei into egg cells and central cells of isolated maize embryo sacs. *Zygote* **2**, 29 (1994).
42. C.M. Williams, G. Zhang, D.D. Cass, Characterization of calcium uptake in isolated maize sperm cells. *Journal of Plant Physiology* **150**, 560 (1997).
43. C.M. Williams, G. Zhang, M. Michalak, D.D. Cass, Calcium-induced protein phosphorylation and changes in levels of calmodulin and calreticulin in maize sperm cells. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **10**, 83 (1997).
44. G. Zhang, D. Liu, D.D. Cass, Calcium-induced sperm fusion in *Zea mays* L. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **10**, 74 (1997).
45. G. Zhang *et al.*, Effects of calcium, magnesium, potassium and boron on sperm cells isolated from pollen of *Zea mays* L. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **8**, 113 (1995).
46. L. Chen, L. Shao, J. Wang, Z. Yang, Isolation and purification of sperm cell plasma membrane glycoproteins of *Zea mays* by affinity chromatography. *Chinese Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* **3**, 339 (1998).
47. M.L. Engel, A. Chaboud, C. Dumas, S. McCormick, Sperm cells of *Zea mays* have a complex complement of mRNAs. *The Plant Journal* **34**, 697 (2003).
48. J.E. Faure *et al.*, Double fertilization in maize: the two male gametes from a pollen grain have the ability to fuse with egg cells. *The Plant Journal* **33**, 1051 (2003).

49. E. Kranz, J. Bautor, H. Lörz, In vitro fertilization of single, isolated gametes of maize mediated by electrofusion. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **4**, 12 (1991).
50. J.E. Faure, H.L. Mogensen, C. Dumas, H. Lörz, E. Kranz, Karyogamy after electrofusion of single egg and sperm cell protoplasts from maize: cytological evidence and time course. *The Plant Cell* **5**, 747 (1993).
51. E. Kranz, H. Lörz, In vitro fertilization with isolated, single gametes results in zygotic embryogenesis and fertile maize plants. *The Plant Cell* **5**, 739 (1993).
52. J.E. Faure, C. Digonnet, C. Dumas, An in vitro system for adhesion and fusion of maize gametes. *Science* **263**, 1598 (1994).
53. E. Kranz, P. von Wiegen, H. Quader, H. Lörz, Endosperm development after fusion of isolated, single maize sperm and central cells in vitro. *The Plant Cell* **10**, 511 (1998).
54. M.X. Sun *et al.*, A reliable protocol for direct detection of lectin binding sites on the plasma membrane of a single living sperm cell in maize. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **15**, 53 (2002).
55. M.X. Sun *et al.*, Fluorophore-conjugated lectin labeling of the cell surface of isolated male and female gametes, central cells and synergids before and after fertilization in maize. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **15**, 159 (2002).
56. X.B. Peng, M.X. Sun, H.Y. Yang, A novel in vitro system for gamete fusion in maize. *Cell Research* **15**, 734 (2005).
57. E. Kranz, J. Bautor, H. Lörz, Electrofusion-mediated transmission of cytoplasmic organelles through the in vitro fertilization process, fusion of sperm cells with synergids and central cells, and cell reconstitution in maize. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **4**, 17 (1991).
58. E. Kranz, H. Lörz, In vitro fertilization of maize by single egg and sperm cell protoplast fusion mediated by high calcium and high pH. *Zygote* **2**, 125 (1994).
59. C. Saito *et al.*, Angiosperm species that produce sperm cell pairs or generative cells with polarized distribution of DNA-containing organelles. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **15**, 167 (2002).
60. E. Matthys-Rochon, C. Dumas, male germ unit: retrospect and prospects. In: *Plant sperm cells as tools for biotechnology*. Eds. HJ Wilms and CJ Keijzer (1988).
61. C.S. Misra *et al.*, Transcriptomics of Arabidopsis sperm cells at single-cell resolution. *Plant Reproduction* **32**, 29 (2019).
62. D.Y. Wang *et al.*, The Levels of male gametic mitochondrial DNA are highly regulated in angiosperms with regard to mitochondrial inheritance. *The Plant Cell* **22**, 2402 (2010).
63. F. Borges *et al.*, Comparative transcriptomics of Arabidopsis sperm cells. *Plant Physiology* **148**, 1168 (2008).
64. N. Chumak, M. Mosiolek, V.K. Schoft, Sample preparation and fractionation of Arabidopsis thaliana sperm and vegetative cell nuclei by FACS. *Bio-protocol* **5**, e1664 (2015).
65. M.R. Santos, C. Bispo, J.D. Becker, Isolation of Arabidopsis pollen, sperm cells, and vegetative nuclei by fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS). In: *Plant Germline Development: Methods and Protocols*, A. Schmidt, Ed. (Springer New York, New York, NY, pp. 193-210. (2017).
66. L. Ichino *et al.*, Single-nucleus RNA-seq reveals that MBD5, MBD6, and SILENZIO maintain silencing in the vegetative cell of developing pollen. *Cell Reports* **41**, 111699 (2022).
67. T. Buttress *et al.*, Histone H2B.8 compacts flowering plant sperm through chromatin phase separation. *Nature* (2022).
68. J. Long *et al.*, Nurse cell-derived small RNAs define paternal epigenetic inheritance in Arabidopsis. *Science* **373**, eabh0556 (2021).
69. M. Borg *et al.*, Targeted reprogramming of H3K27me3 resets epigenetic memory in plant paternal chromatin. *Nature Cell Biology* **22**, 621 (2020).
70. P.H. Hsieh *et al.*, Arabidopsis male sexual lineage exhibits more robust maintenance of CG methylation than somatic tissues. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **113**, 15132 (2016).
71. C.A. Ibarra *et al.*, Active DNA Demethylation in plant companion cells reinforces transposon methylation in gametes. *Science* **337**, 1360 (2012).
72. J.P. Calarco *et al.*, Reprogramming of DNA Methylation in pollen guides epigenetic inheritance via small RNA. *Cell* **151**, 194 (2012).

73. C.S. Misra, A.G.G. Sousa, P. M. Barros, A. Kermanov, J. D. Becker, Cell-type-specific alternative splicing in the Arabidopsis germline. *Plant Physiology* (2023)(<https://doi.org/10.1093/plphys/kiac574>)
74. A. Wibowo *et al.*, Hyperosmotic stress memory in Arabidopsis is mediated by distinct epigenetically labile sites in the genome and is restricted in the male germline by DNA glycosylase activity. *eLife* **5**, e13546 (2016).
75. S. Khouider *et al.*, Male fertility in Arabidopsis requires active DNA demethylation of genes that control pollen tube function. *Nature Communications* **12**, 410 (2021).
76. M. Borg *et al.*, Epigenetic reprogramming rewires transcription during the alternation of generations in Arabidopsis. *eLife* **10**, e61894 (2021).
77. S. He, M. Vickers, J. Zhang, X. Feng, Natural depletion of histone H1 in sex cells causes DNA demethylation, heterochromatin decondensation and transposon activation. *eLife* **8**, e42530 (2019).
78. V. K. Schoft *et al.*, Function of the DEMETER DNA glycosylase in the Arabidopsis thaliana male gametophyte. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **108**, 8042 (2011).
79. H. Deng, Y.Y. Wang, X.Y. Zhu, H.Q. Tian, Generative and sperm cell isolation in Bauhinia blakeana (Fabaceae). *Annales Botanici Fennici* **49**, 1 (2012).
80. J. Nielsen, P. Olesen, Isolation of sperm cells from the trinucleate pollen of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*). In: *Plant sperm cells as tools for biotechnology*. eds HJ Wilms and CJ Keijzer (1988).
81. P.E. Taylor, J. Kenrick, C.K. Blomstedt, R.B. Knox, Sperm cells of the pollen tubes of Brassica: Ultrastructure and isolation. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **4**, 226 (1991).
82. M. Yong-sheng, Y. Hong-yuan, Mass isolation and preservation of viable sperm cells in Brassica campestris var. purpurea. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **33**, 649 (1991).
83. T. Hough, M.B. Singh, I.J. Smart, R.B. Knox, Immunofluorescent screening of monoclonal antibodies to surface antigens of animal and plant cells bound to polycarbonate membranes. *Journal of Immunological Methods* **92**, 103 (1986).
84. E. Matthys-Rochon, S. Detchepare, V. Wagner, P. Roeckel, C. Dumas, Isolation and characterization of viable sperm cells from tricellular pollen grains. In: *Sexual reproduction in higher plants*. (Springer, 245-250 (1988).
85. C.K. Blomstedt, H. Xu, M.B. Singh, R.B. Knox, The isolation and purification of surface specific proteins of somatic and reproductive protoplasts of lily and rapeseed. *Physiologia Plantarum* **85**, 396 (1992).
86. W. Zhang *et al.*, A phased genome based on single sperm sequencing reveals crossover pattern and complex relatedness in tea plants. *The Plant Journal* **105**, 197 (2021).
87. W. Deng, Y. Xie, Y. Qiu, Isolation of sperm and egg cells from pepper. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* **143**, 310 (2018).
88. L.Y. Zhang, Q.G. Guo, G.L. Liang. (International Society for Horticultural Science (ISHS), Leuven, Belgium, 2007), pp. 193-196.
89. L.Y. Zhang, Q.G. Guo, Q. He, X. Li, G. Liang. (International Society for Horticultural Science (ISHS), Leuven, Belgium, 2007), pp. 533-537.
90. C. Saito *et al.*, Unequal distribution of DNA-containing organelles in generative and sperm cells of Erythrinacrista-galli (Fabaceae). *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **12**, 296 (2000).
91. S. Woo, H. Hirano, S. Jong, T. Adachj, Micromanipulation of protoplasts from male gametophytic cells in common buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench.) (2001).
92. Y. Hosokawa *et al.*, Nondestructive isolation of single cultured animal cells by femtosecond laser-induced shockwave. In: *Applied Physics A: Materials Science & Processing* **79**, 795 (2004).
93. D. Southworth, R.B. Knox, Flowering plant sperm cells: Isolation from pollen of Gerbera jamesonii (asteraceae). *Plant Science* **60**, 273 (1989).
94. Z.J. a. F.Ruwen, Mass Isolation of viable sperm cells from the pollen of Liriodendron chinense. *Journal of Nanjing Forestry University* **42**, 12 (1999).
95. H. Xu *et al.*, Isolation and characterization of male-germ-cell transcripts in Nicotiana tabacum. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **14**, 339 (2002).
96. H.Q. Tian, S.D. Russell, Micromanipulation of male and female gametes of Nicotiana tabacum: I. Isolation of gametes. *Plant Cell Reports* **16**, 555 (1997).

97. Y. Cao, A. Reece, S.D. Russell, Isolation of viable sperm cells from tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*). *Zygote* **4**, 81 (1996).
98. K.F. Fang, M.X. Sun, Probing lectin binding sites on isolated viable generative and sperm cells of tobacco. *Plant Science* **168**, 1259 (2005).
99. Y.H. Yang *et al.*, Isolation of two populations of sperm cells and microelectrophoresis of pairs of sperm cells from pollen tubes of tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*). *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **18**, 47 (2005).
100. H.Q. Tian, S.D. Russell, Micromanipulation of male and female gametes of *Nicotiana tabacum*: II. Preliminary attempts for in vitro fertilization and egg cell culture. *Plant Cell Reports* **16**, 657 (1997).
101. M.X. Sun, A. Moscatelli, H. Y. Yang, M. Cresti, In vitro double fertilization in *Nicotiana tabacum* (L.): fusion behavior and gamete interaction traced by video-enhanced microscopy. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **12**, 267 (2000).
102. M.X. Sun, A. Moscatelli, H.-Y. Yang, M. Cresti, In vitro double fertilization in *Nicotiana tabacum* (L.): the role of cell volume in cell fusion. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **13**, 225 (2001).
103. K. Fang, P. Lu, T. Yu, in *2010 4th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering*. (IEEE, 2010), pp. 1-4.
104. H.P. Xin *et al.*, Expressed sequence-tag analysis of tobacco sperm cells reveals a unique transcriptional profile and selective persistence of paternal transcripts after fertilization. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **24**, 37 (2011).
105. S.D. Russell, Isolation of sperm cells from pollen of *Plumbago zeylanica*. *Plant Physiology* **81**, 317 (1986).
106. Z. Zhang, S.D. Russell, Sperm cell surface characteristics of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. in relation to transport in the embryo sac. *Planta* **208**, 539 (1999).
107. Z. Zhang, H. Xu, M.B. Singh, S.D. Russell, Isolation and collection of two populations of viable sperm cells from the pollen of *Plumbago zeylanica*. *Zygote* **6**, 295 (1998).
108. M.B. Singh *et al.*, Developmental expression of polyubiquitin genes and distribution of ubiquitinated proteins in generative and sperm cells. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **14**, 325 (2002).
109. X. Gou, T. Yuan, X. Wei, S.D. Russell, Gene expression in the dimorphic sperm cells of *Plumbago zeylanica*: transcript profiling, diversity, and relationship to cell type. *The Plant Journal* **60**, 33 (2009).
110. M.Y. Kim *et al.*, DNA demethylation by ROS1a in rice vegetative cells promotes methylation in sperm. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **116**, 9652 (2019).
111. Y. Lu, L. Wei, T. Wang, Methods to isolate a large amount of generative cells, sperm cells and vegetative nuclei from tomato pollen for “omics” analysis. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **6**, (2015).
112. L. Liu *et al.*, Transcriptomics analyses reveal the molecular roadmap and long non-coding RNA landscape of sperm cell lineage development. *The Plant Journal* **96**, 421 (2018).
113. Y. Lu, Y. Song, L. Liu, T. Wang, DNA methylation dynamics of sperm cell lineage development in tomato. *The Plant Journal* **105**, 565 (2021).
114. S.J. Yang, D.M. Wei, H.Q. Tian, Isolation of sperm cells, egg cells, synergids and central cells from *Solanum verbascifolium* L. *Journal of Plant Biochemistry and Biotechnology* **24**, 400 (2015).
115. C. Theunis, J. Van Went, Isolation of sperm cells from *Spinacia oleracea* from mature pollen. *Sexual Plant Reproduction* **2**, 97 (1989).
116. C. Theunis, Ultrastructural analysis of *Spinacia oleracea* sperm cells isolated from mature pollen grains. *Protoplasma* **158**, 176 (1990).
117. A.C. van Aelst, C.H. Theunis, J.L. van Went, Freeze-fracture studies on isolated sperm cells of *Spinacia oleracea* L. *Protoplasma* **153**, 204 (1990).
118. S.H. Chen, J.P. Liao, A.X. Kuang, H.Q. Tian, Isolation of two populations of sperm cells from the pollen tube of *Torenia fournieri*. *Plant Cell Reports* **25**, 1138 (2006).
119. P. Vági, K. Imre, Z. Kristóf, Isolation of living sperm cells and in vitro fusion of *Torenia fournieri* gametes. *International Journal of Horticultural Science* **12**, 81 (2006).
120. X.F. Chen, W.D. Li, Isolation and preservation of viable sperm cells of *Ulmus pumila*. *Acta Botanica Sinica* **40**, 122 (1998).
121. I. Julca *et al.*, Comparative transcriptomic analysis reveals conserved programmes underpinning organogenesis and reproduction in land plants. *Nature Plants* **7**, 1143 (2021).